

The summary of the survey on the "GrInShield – 101079151 in collaboration with EUTA – Workshop on Project Writing and Management" held in April 2023

Questions:

GrInShield workshop feedback

We would kindly appreciate your feedback on the "GrInShield – 101079151 in collaboration with EUTA – Workshop on Project Writing and Management" held in April 2023.

* Indicates required question

First and last name *

Your answer

Have you applied for internationally funded projects before attending the workshop? *

No

Yes

Other: _____

How were you satisfied with the level of new information you received at the workshop? *

Not Satisfied

Satisfied

Very Satisfied

Have you applied for any internationally funded projects since the Workshop? *

Yes

No

If you have applied for new projects, please specify the funding source and if it was granted.

Your answer

Has the participation at the workshop introduced you to some new perspectives *
on the obligations and tasks involved in the project writing and execution?
(please describe them)

Your answer

What aspects of this workshop were most useful or valuable? *

- Horizon Europe Framework
- Project writing
- Budgeting
- Implementation

How likely are you to attend a workshop on project writing and management *
again?

- not likely
- likely
- definitely

Please leave any additional feedback:

Your answer

Summary of results:

Q1:

Have you applied for internationally funded projects before attending the workshop?

14 responses

Q2:

How were you satisfied with the level of new information you received at the workshop?

14 responses

Q3:

Have you applied for any internationally funded projects since the Workshop?

14 responses

Q4:

If you have applied for new projects, please specify the funding source and if it was granted.

5 responses

Yes, I applied to Fondazione Bruno Kessler for Short Term Mission at Institute for Photonics and Nanotechnologies (IFN) of National Research Council (CNR) in Trento, Italy.

various EU funded projects

Horizon Europe, Bilateral Projects (SRB-ITA), Science Funds, Republic of Serbia, no new projects yet

European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme, under evaluation

NATO

Q5:

Has the participation at the workshop introduced you to some new perspectives on the obligations and tasks involved in the project writing and execution?

14 responses

Yes

Yes.

Budgeting planning and execution

Better understanding of respecting scheduled tasks within the project and its connections to other project deliverables

Global plan at start, rolling-wave planning and milestone orientation.

Yes definitely, it shed the light on the complete application process for European funds.

It has, it was very educational.

Budgeting

Q6:

What aspects of this workshop were most useful or valuable?

14 responses

Q7:

How likely are you to attend a workshop on project writing and management again?

14 responses

Q8:

Please leave any additional feedback:

3 responses

A very nicely organized workshop, where we learned a lot of new things related to all aspects of writing a project.

WS was organized in a practical way to explain and demonstrate elements of project proposals, key factors to success, and clarification of the budget, continuous reporting, with a lot of time for questions and discussion, and great lecturers.

Excellent organization of the training! Many compliments to the organizer!